

QUIZ**LAST NAME: NORMAN-HANSEN****FIRST NAME: JARLE****PROGRAM CODE: DGE****COURSE CODE: ACA 401-D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSWord on Windows 11.

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **How does an international abstract in a doctoral dissertation meet academic standards?**

- It should be as brief as possible and only include the research problem, findings, and conclusions and be limited to one page.
- It should be extensive, include all key elements of the dissertation, and consist of at least 350 words.
- It should include all key elements of the dissertation and consist of a limited number of words (350).¹**
- It should include the most interesting part of the dissertation to get the reader interested. It should be written in a passive voice with personal nouns like I and we.

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Quality Dissertation. A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, Fourth ed. (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2019), 68.

2. **Why must a literature review be included in a doctoral dissertation?**

- To show academia that you are up to date and have spent time on the available literature.
- To give an overview of the existing literature and research in the field, synthesize, identify gaps, and get a basis for developing your research proposal.²**
- To give a summarized overview of existing research in the field and place your research herein.
- To give the reader an overview and show that you, as a researcher, are well informed. By citing the literature, the writer gives evidence and avoids plagiarism.

3. **Why should you use Grammarly or a similar data tool when writing an academic paper?**

- To improve your language skills and find misspellings.
- To improve your language, find misspellings, check for plagiarism, and have a word count.³**
- To avoid plagiarism and check for misspellings so the reader can concentrate on the research.
- To help you be more accurate in complicated academic language and grammar.

² Ibid., 383.

³ *Grammarly Tutorial: Making Use of Grammarly Premium & An Overview of Grammarly for Google Docs*, 2018, accessed September 2, 2023, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FKRBvTOLo1M>.

4. **Latin abbreviations are common in writing. In academic writing, Latin abbreviations should be:**

- Used frequently to increase the academic standard of writing.
- Spelled out to avoid misunderstanding.
- Avoided as much as possible. However, they can be used in tables, notes, references, and within parentheses.⁴**
- Avoided as much as possible and only use when citing.

5. **Why is Dr. Adu talking about ontology in his YouTube video?**

- To introduce a complicated word that enhances a researcher's language skills and makes the language more academic.
- To better understand research and how qualitative research differs from quantitative research.
- To help in understanding how complicated qualitative research is.
- To help in understanding the background of the researcher, which is critical in qualitative research as there are multiple realities.⁵**

6. **In an introduction to a response paper at Euclid University, you should:**

- Summarize your work and write an abstract of the paper.
- Limit the introduction to your initial conclusions and findings.

⁴ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 44.

⁵ Philip Adu, "Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study," March 6, 2016, accessed November 5, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708>.

Introduce the topic area with a sentence or two. Answer the question with a thesis statement and provide a summary or “road map” of the paper.⁶

Summarize your work with all key elements to let the reader know your views, findings, and conclusions.

7. **What is the general rule for using numbers in academic writing?**

Spell out when part of the text for numbers up to one hundred, unless for a series of numbers, in tables and figures, or when used with percent. Higher numbers are in Arabic.⁷

The writer can do whatever suits best if the usage is consistent.

To be precise, the writing of numbers is always in Arabic.

Numbers are always written out in academic writing, except for in tables and charts.

8. **How many citations are appropriate per page in a doctoral dissertation?**

The rule is a maximum of two per page.

As many as possible to support your research and make the reader understand you have a good overview.

There is no rule, but they should be limited to three.⁸

As few as possible and never more than one per page. Otherwise, plagiarism is possible.

⁶ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 10.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, ed. Booth, Wayne C. et al., Ninth. (Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 339.

⁸ Euclid University, “Initial Student Orientation 2022,” <https://euclid.egnyte.com/fl/IPSrNYvHok>.

9. **How does a reference to a doctoral dissertation differ from a reference to a book in a Turabian-style author-date reference list?**

- The title is in italics and enclosed in quotation marks. The type of work must be listed as “Ph.D diss.,” and the university comes before the place of publishing.
- The title is in italics and enclosed in quotation marks. Otherwise, the same.
- The author’s first name comes before the family name. The title is in Roman type and enclosed in quotation marks.
- The title is in Roman type and enclosed in quotation marks. “PhD diss.” is used for the type of work and the name of the university comes before the place of publication.⁹**

10. **Bloomberg and Volpe use the acronym ABD. What does it stand for?**

- Always Blind when Doing refers to the fact that you have trouble seeing your faults when writing. Hence, proofreading after a few days (or by someone else) is recommended. Grammarly is a helpful tool that checks spelling and grammar.
- Attention to Bibliography Details. Citing is part of academic writing and needs to be correct. Even with tools like Zotero, the writer must pay attention to all the details.
- All-But-Done refers to engaging in too many parts of a dissertation without a plan. Good advice is to write in increments, so the work becomes coherent and does not become overwhelming. This also reduces the chance of procrastination.

⁹ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 336.

- All But Dissertation refers to doctoral students who fail to complete their dissertation.¹⁰**

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¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Quality Dissertation. A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, 27.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.